

MANAGEMENT OF ACCOUNTS RECEIVABLE AND ACCOUNTS PAYABLE

Malikova Mukhsina Gahramanovna

Jizzakh "Sambhram" University

MBA magestri

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7493690>

Annotation

Timely and complete receipt of receivables serves the continuity, continuity and effective conduct of the activities of each business entity. In this case, it is required to focus on achieving the self-fulfillment of the obligations of the buyer and customers in the prescribed manner.

Because the untimely receipt of receivables creates a deficit in cash funds in enterprises and organizations. As a result, the need of the enterprise for working assets to finance current activities increases, and in turn, as a result of the inability to timely cover the accounts payable, the level of solvency is reduced.

Base words and phrases: liabilities, financial stability, solvency, receivables, accounts receivable, creditor snow

Timely and complete receipt of receivables serves the continuity, continuity and effective conduct of the activities of each business entity. It can be seen from this that every business entity has the need to focus its main attention not only on debiratory debts, but also on accounts payable, and the aspects that are being brought represent the need to manage accounts receivable and accounts payable on the scale of enterprises.

Therefore, it is also necessary to note that in the management of accounts receivable and Accounts Payable, the main attention is paid to ensuring their mutual compatibility in terms of quantity and time. The main purpose of managing accounts receivable is not to allow them to delay, not to carry out fines or use other methods. And the main goal of managing accounts payable is the timing of financial obligations

As reasons for the occurrence of accounts receivable and Accounts Payable, the following can be cited:

1. The validity of a chain link between enterprises subordinate to one system. An example of this is the supply of products grown on state purchase to the state, in turn, accounts receivable, which are taken into account by the state in the process of supplying the necessary material resources to the economic entity, and the procedure for their compensation.

2. The occurrence of cases of financial instability at the enterprise. That is, a decrease in the state of financial stability of customers and buyers of their obligations leads to the fact that the receivables did not come on time. Cases of occurrence of this condition are observed in practice even as a result of insufficient study of customers and buyers by the enterprise.

- 3. Low exposure to accounts receivable and accounts payable, i.e. low exposure to financial penalties or other measures that apply in cases where obligations are not met on time, can lead to a su'ny increase in accounts receivable and accounts receivable.

- 4. The occurrence of cases of macroeconomic instability. It should be noted that the circumstances of the stability of the financial system in the microdistrict also cause an increase in accounts receivable and accounts payable. In this case, it can also bring situations that can occur as a result of an increase in the budget deficit, an increase in taxes, a violation of cooperation relations with other mammals, etc.

- 5. The validity of the advance payment. In financial relations, advance payments are used in order to guarantee payment. If the implementation of the advance payment is taken into account as a receivable in one subject, then in another subject the kre

The composition of receivables includes the debts of the buyer and the customer, the composition of receivables of the allocated divisions includes the debts of the buyer and the customer, allocated debts of divisions, debts of subsidiaries and dependent economic societies, employees include payments made to suppliers of goods and contractors, payments to the budget for taxes and fees, payments to target state funds and insurance payments, debts to the founders ' authorized capital by shares, debts to employees for other operations and other necessary funds.

When managing accounts receivable, it is advisable to pay attention to:

Setting a clear limit and norm on receivables. This practice allows continuity of activity by effectively organizing the movement of funds directly.

The establishment of a clear limit and norm on receivables is determined based on the amount and time of the funds required for the continuity of activity. Development of specific schemes for consumer loans, commercial loans (development of payment schedules). Consumer credit to an individual his it is a loan that is issued for the purchase of goods (works, services) in order to meet consumer needs. A commercial loan, on the other hand, is a component of a consumer loan and implies the transfer of goods on credit.\

Covered and non-covered letters of credit are subject to recall and conscription can be in non-removable form. If the letter of credit does not provide for its non-recall, such a letter of credit is a letter of credit to be called.

Used literature:

1. Investopedia (2018). Accounts receivable-AR. Obtained: investopedia.com.
2. HTMW team (2013). Settlement accounts receivable management. How the market works. Obtained from: education. Howthemarketworks.com.
3. Graydon (2018). Management of accounts receivable. Olingan:graydon.nl.

